

Studies in Fluorinated 1,3-Diketones and Related Compounds. Part—XIV : Search for New NMR Shift Reagents

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New fluorinated europium 1,3-diketones have been synthesised and characterized by ir, ^1H -nmr and ^{19}F -nmr spectral studies as possible nmr shift reagents and the shifts produced with *n*-hexanol, *n*-heptanol, *p*-fluoroaniline and *m*-trifluoromethylaniline have been studied.

^1H -NMR spectra of simple organic molecules are not complicated as the resonances do not overlap at easily accessible field strengths but in the spectra of complex molecules, many resonances do overlap and important structural information may be lost.

Hinckley¹, in 1969, reported the potential of rare earth chelates as nmr shift reagents and described the successful applications of lanthanide shift reagents to a wide range of structural problems. Horrocks² tested several $\text{Ln}(\text{thd})_3$ reagents, some of which caused still greater shifts than the classical Eu and Pr chelates.

A number of similar reagents, e.g. *tris* (dibenzoylmethanate) and *tris* (benzoylacetonates), were also reported but did not appear to offer any particular advantage over the dipivaloylmethanates. Subsequently, Feibush *et al*³ reported fluorinated lanthanide shift reagents. These reagents proved

to be superior to their non-fluorinated analogues as they provide improved solubility due to perfluoroalkyl groups and the presence of fluorine atoms on the ligands confers higher Lewis acidity on the lanthanide. This higher acidity makes it a more versatile shift reagent for general applications.

Our recent interest in the chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones prompted us to examine some new fluorinated 1,3-diketoneeuropium chelates as possible nmr shift reagents and thus add to the variety of useful lanthanide shift reagents. For this purpose, we have selected [4,4,5,5,6,6,6-heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-hexanedionato]europium(III) [(hfh)₃Eu] and [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]europium(III) [(pfp)₃Eu], synthesized by us earlier⁴, as possible nmr shift reagents and have studied the shifts produced with *n*-hexanol, *n*-heptanol, *p*-fluoroaniline and *m*-trifluoromethylaniline using a 60 MHz spectrometer model RB-12.

TABLE I—SHIFT STUDIES OF *n*-HEXANOL, *n*-HEPTANOL, *p*-FLUOROANILINE, *m*-TRIFLUOROMETHYLANILINE BY $\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$ AND $\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$ IN ODCl_3 (1 ml)

Sl. No.	Shift reagent	Nucleophile	Ratio of Shift Reagent : Nucleophile (in mg)	Time in hr	Position of different signals in δ ppm				
					$-\text{OH}$	$-\text{CH}_2$ attached to OH	$(\text{OH})_2 / (\text{OH})_3$	$-\text{NH}_2$	Aromatic protons
1.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	Control	1	4.25	3.55	1.4	0.9	
2.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	6 : 1	2	3.5	3.60	1.3	0.85	
3.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	6 : 1	3.5	3.7	3.65	1.35	0.9	
4.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	6 : 1	24	3.9	3.65	1.35	0.9	
5.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>n</i> -hexanol	Control	1	4.45	3.55	1.4	0.9	
6.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>n</i> -hexanol	5 : 1	2	4.0	4.2	1.4	0.9	
7.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>n</i> -hexanol	5 : 1	24	3.9	4.0	1.3	0.85	
8.	$\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	Control	1	4.25	3.55	1.4	0.9	
9.	$\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	6 : 1	1.5	4.15	3.5	1.25	0.85	
10.	$\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	3 : 1	2	4.35	3.45	1.20	0.75	
11.	$\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$	<i>n</i> -heptanol	2 : 1	70	4.65	3.6	1.35	0.95	
12.	$\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$	<i>n</i> -hexanol	Control	1	4.45	3.55	1.4	0.9	
13.	$\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$	<i>n</i> -hexanol	5 : 1	2.5	3.15	3.5	1.3	0.85	
14.	$\text{Eu}(\text{hfh})_3$	<i>n</i> -hexanol	5 : 1	60	3.45	3.5	1.3	0.85	
15.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>p</i> -fluoroaniline	Control	1					3.5
16.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>p</i> -fluoroaniline	3 : 1	1					5.9
17.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	<i>m</i> -trifluoromethylaniline	Control	1					3.65
18.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	" "	4 : 1	1					5.15
19.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	" "	2 : 1	1.5					5.0
20.	$\text{Eu}(\text{pfp})_3$	" "	2 : 1	48					5.15

Experimental

Synthesis of polyfluorinated 1,3-diketones : These polyfluorinated 1,3-diketones have already been reported by us^{4,5}.

Europium 1,3-diketonates : EuCl₃ (0.004 mole), dissolved in a minimal amount of methanol, was added dropwise to a methanolic solution of β -diketonatoenolate anion (0.012 mole). The complex was precipitated by slow addition of water to the resulting methanolic solution. The precipitated europium 1,3-diketonates were crystallized from benzene and dried in vacuum, over phosphorus pentaoxide, for 24 hr⁶.

Results and Discussion

The substrate associates with the complex at the hydroxyl group (*n*-hexanol, *n*-heptanol) or the amino group (*p*-fluoroaniline or *m*-trifluoromethyl-aniline) and the induced shifts decrease rapidly

with increasing distance of protons from the hydroxyl group. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

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